

“Alternative analysis of localization of resort hotel planned in Brudzeń Landscape Park”

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ABSTRACT

Fig. 1. Landscapes of the BLP

Fig. 2. Lakes within the BLP

The *Brudzeń Landscape Park* (further *BLP*) is an environmentally protected area located in the centre of Poland in *Masovian Voivodeship* (*Województwo Mazowieckie*) near the historical city of *Płock*. It includes forests, numerous little lakes and famous *Vistula River* and very beautiful surroundings. The unique nature of the park as well as its location in the centre of Poland enables perfect conditions for the construction of the SPA-hotel resort within the BLP Park.

The main purpose of the hotel is to let guests enjoy the nature, recover their health and explore Poland. Current research focuses on the GIS analysis of the most optimal place location for the hotel within the BLP Park. The alternative environmental analysis of three possible locations has been used for the final decision. The spatial analysis was implemented using ArcGIS 9.2 (ArcMap and ArcCatalog).

INTRODUCTION

According to the Act on Protection of Nature of 2004, a Landscape Park is defined as "an area protected because of its natural, historical, cultural and scenic values, for the purpose of conserving and popularizing those values in conditions of balanced development."

In the landscape park business activity can be with certain restrictions; for example, does not include the erection of new buildings (with the exception of the local population needed). Park should serve a recreation and sightseeing, tourism, leisure and education.

General geographic information and landscapes

The research area of the project focuses on *Brudzeń Landscape Park*, which was established in 1988.

The BLP surface is 3 171 ha and its buffer zone 4 397 ha. Within the area between the Wkra and Drwęca River valleys, Brudzeń Landscape Park

is undoubtedly the most valuable natural area of the northwest Masovian Region. The decision of the creation of the Park was based on the uniqueness of the natural landscape, a lot cultural and natural values and diversity of geomorphologic forms.

This type of terrain park is of high value due to the variety of the processes accompanying with the last glaciation period. Both edges of the valley of the river have undergone geological development: flat areas near the Skrwa and almost vertical walls. The dominating

Fig. 5. Walking in the BLP

types within the forest communities are broad-leaved and mixed forests. The dominant tree species are hornbeam, oak, linden, maple and sycamore, and admixture are birch, pine, spruce and beech and a few of rare plants. The common species in the woods are: wild boar, roe deer, fox and badger; in the rivers: beaver and otter. There are many rare species of the birds and lot of fishes as well. On the area of the BLP there are currently two nature reserves: '*Sikora*' includes the 12 - km part of bank of the river and reserve of

'luminous oak' 'Brwilno' is located in the southern part. Another important function of the Park is to protect and popularize the cultural values of the area.

There are a lot of historic buildings or churches and monuments like the mighty oak tree growing in a historic park in *Srebrna*.

Analysis of the particular environmental components

Geology, Quaternary and mineral deposits,

Scenery in BLP mostly was made during glacial age; to be exact influence during the last one called the Würm glaciation (the last years of the Pleistocene). Generally the most often the soil in this area is sand and loam, especially glacial sand which was left after moving back a glacier. Because of that type of drift substratum is infertile. Only near 10 per cent of the area soils are good to cultivation (soil class: 2 and 3). But most of them are poor with very severe limitations that restrict the choice of plants or that require very careful management.

In the BLP there are a large number of oak and hornbeam forest and maple-tilia forest near the river. There are only a few places with meadows.

The area of Brudzeń Landscape Park is covered with Quaternary Pleistocene and Holocene deposits. The diversified structure of superficial deposits and soils in the Park formed thanks to various Tertiary and Quaternary geological processes. The parent rocks of the soils in the area described consists mostly of loose, weakly loamy and loamy sands, light and medium loams, and silts. The geology of the research areas is flat, lowland with evidence of the last glaciation. The mineral resources of the area have deposits of limestone and dolomite.

Agricultural resources and soil

In the BLP there are Haplic Podzols, Dystric Arenosols (rusty soils), Eutric Cambisols (brown soils), Luvisols, Mollic Gleysols (black earths); in the valleys, there are Histosols (mud-peat soils), alluvial soils (Fluvisols) and Mollic Gleysols (black earths) The formation of the soils is related to the extent of warm or wet forests, with broadleaf trees, first of all of the oak. The research area lies in the Mazovia region which is characteristics for its agricultural dominance, yet due to its central location, the region is an important intersection in terms of transport. In addition to industry and services, the research area also has a rapidly developing agricultural industry—in Mazovia region 94.91 percent of arable land belongs to private farms (the largest proportion in Poland). The rural population in the Mazovia region is 1, 814,000 - 35.8 percent of the province total, or 12.3 percent of total rural population in Poland. The dominant soils in the area are sandy and podsol.

Environmental protection

According to the directive of provincial governor, the Brudzenski Landscape Park case was created to save meandering river Skrwa Prawa and connected with it two others channel complex and also to protect forest ecosystems as well as rare and protected species of fungi, plants and animals and their habitats. Other aim is protect natural, cultural and historic values. It is forbidden ventures which can have a significant impact on the environment in the Park as well as killing animals, destroying their shelters and places for reproduction, damaging tree-covered areas, rocks, fossils etc. It is also prohibited within the BLP every land moving which would permanently deform the terrain and change water conditions.

Noise & acoustic climate, vibration

Noise has long been recognized as a potential threat to humans' hearing. With noise sources constantly increasing in today's environment, noise can become harmful to the well-being of the public at large. Impacts on human mental and physical health can often be attributed to noise pollution and, as a result, noise control is a critical challenge. Yet in the territory of the BLP we consider this potential environmental threat as minimal due to the isolation of this place from the cities, highways, and other major sources of noise.

Anthropogenic & archaeological factors, human activities

In the BLP there are many different monuments like churches, manor houses, mansions or old mills. In Brudzien Duży and Sikórz there are restored palace and park, in Brwilno original wooden architecture and one hundred years old and still functioning water mill in Radotki. In Brudzen's forest stand out of size and conservation status an early grad (Slavic settlement). Found there pottery from the time of Celtic and later. Recent history related to the Polish people during World War II commemorates places of national memorial in the forests near Brudzeń and Brwilno.

Social-economical and industrial factors

The area is not densely populated due to the location of the *BLP* and protected zone, so that the anthropogenic pressure on the local environment has low level. Płock is in short distance from the BLP. This city has about 126,000 inhabitants using the park as a peace place to rest and relax. Walking, doing some sports like fishing, cycling or horse riding are examples of touristic- holiday meaning of this green area. Between Płock and border of the park there is a

powerful industry: PKN Orlen. This is a major European oil refiner, and petrol retailer. At a time when it was decided to build the refinery-petrochemical conglomerate near city, even not perceived closeness of forested river valleys, because of the search for flat areas, not threatened flood waters, with a stable ground. A huge field was placed next to the city, outside the network of nearest rivers. Hopefully wildlife has survived despite many years of experience with sewage, gas emissions, waste and noise and other harmful influence of the environment.

DATA

The project included spatial vector and raster data in GIS format.

At the beginning of our research we did careful analysis and investigation of all available spatial data and information.

The set of different data has been georeferenced on the Datum “GCS_ETRF_1989” and projected into the “PUWG-92 coordinate system” - Polish National grid (*Polskie Układy Współrzędnych w ArcGIS*) with central meridian of 19° E.

The full list of the thematic data includes the following spatial layers:

1. Raster map of Digital Elevation Model (DEM) showing heights within the study areas (ranging from 50 m as the lowest until 128 m as highest)
2. Vector layers of soils; the dominant type in the areas is sandy soils, yet there are other types as well: fluvisols, podsol, mollic gray sols, etc.
3. Vector layers of tourist popular routes, points (most visited places) and other touristic places (already existing holiday houses and villages)
4. Geological map of the area which also included main types of land cover: aeolian sands, alluvial sands, clays and ice-dammed loams, glacial sands, peats, colluviums, etc
5. Polygon vector layer containing information about biodiversity, communities (e.g. meadows), plants, vegetation types in the following layers: *speech_r_ch_p.shp*, *communities_a.shp*, *diversity_centres_a.shp*. Examples of common species within the research area: mezeleon, common snowdrop, Turk’s cap lily, white water lily, etc.
6. *Communications.shp* which contains roads with major and minor order of importance

7. Different types of forests (alder, ashen, mixed, coniferous, riparian, etc)
8. Block of hydrographical layers incl. rivers and lakes, watershed and river tributaries
9. Line layer with spatial planning routes where spatial management planning exists
10. Existing farm buildings, production/services areas, etc
11. Zonal vector layer of environmental ranking of the surrounding landscapes (zones_a.shp) with very detailed description of the environmental status of the lands
12. The total area of BLP with buffer zone
13. Borders of the BLP itself and the protection zone
14. Endangered areas :
 - High-, medium- and low-level intensity of settlement arrangement development
 - Areas of intensive tourist activities
 - High-pressure fuel and gas pipelines
 - Archaeological areas endangered by new forms of management
 - Areas of flood (1%) and landslides
15. The block of vector files with info about Cultural resources: existing archaeological sites, restoration areas, registered monuments, cultural landscape protection zones, etc
16. Analytical vector layer containing ecological structures: biocentres and local ecological corridors of three hierarchical levels: local, over-local and country-level.
17. The block of layers “Natural Protection forms” contains specific objects that are protected by the governmental decisions: pp_p.shp: protected plants, spec_r_ch_p.shp: endangered vegetation species (e.g., *bird's nest orchid*, *Turk's cap lily*, *white water lily*, *slender-leaved pondweed*, etc), as well as protected water areas: Jozefowskie Lake and Skrwa mouth. Finally, the rp_lp_a.shp file contains reserve areas such as Sikorz Reserve and Brwilno Reserve.

METHODS

The technological implementation of the GIS-based spatial analysis of the research project is based on the ArcGIS 9.2 software (ArcMap and ArcCatalog modules).

Criteria for the environmental assessment

For the complete analysis of the suitability of the BLP areas to the hotel construction we used different diverse factors of the anthropogenic, economic and environmental character.

We considered as the most important factors the following ones where NO hotel construction can be made:

1. (anthropogenic factors):

- ✓ *archaeological protected areas*, because every society planning must take historically important objects into consideration and take care about our past
- ✓ *areas of high intensity of settlement arrangement development*, as areas already in use and having important social functions
- ✓ *cemeteries*, of course, for the respect of our ancestors
- ✓ areas of intensive tourist activity
- ✓ *archaeological areas* endangered by new forms of management
- ✓ *major tourists objects, such as routes, tourist farms, swimming spots, and existing areas with recreational function*, because we plan to enlarge area for the healthy recreation, not to reduce the existing one
- ✓ *existing monumental and other buildings*, which is logical as destroying building is unreasonable and anti-social

2. (economic)

- *high-pressure fuel and gas pipelines* with buffer zone of 100 meters, as their vicinity is both potentially damaging and not aesthetically for the SPA-hotel
- existing farm buildings with buffer zone of 100 meters
- existing individual recreation buildings
- existing public purpose services

- existing holiday houses, holiday villages

3. (environmental)

- Biocentres and ecological corridors of all three levels (country-, over-local and local)
- Up to 10 meters above Vistula River (because in the worst flood scenario the inundated waters may arise up to 7-8 meters)
- Water bodies (lakes, rivers)
- Strictly protected areas of the high protection level (governmental decisions)
- Avoid *Mollic Gleysoils* as too saturated with groundwater, therefore, unsuitable and dangerous for buildings construction
- Avoid *Luvisols*: having too weak soil profile, these soils make good agricultural land and can be intensively used as precious agricultural resource.
- Geology: avoid construction on the following land cover types: peats, clays, fluvial gravels, muds of valley floors and without outflow depressions, alluvial sands and muds of valley flood plains

RESULTS

I. GIS-Analysis

GIS-Analysis has been implemented on the basis of ArcGIS, using its tools for the spatial analysis and criteria arrangement. To make thorough analysis we first carefully studied thematic layers one-by-one and then created thematic maps of the elements of the environment that are to be analysed.

Analysis of the geological conditions

We used “select by attributes” request to highlight suitable areas suitable for the proposed construction. Analysing the geological layer we

can see that there are morphologically diversified area with a significant number of interior depressions in the area, as a result of a relatively fast and uniform deglaciation.

For our hotel construction the most suitable area would be the highest terrace in the Skrwa Prawa River valley (Fig.7) as to avoid possible floods and locate hotel in the most stable geological area with corresponding soils. From the geomorphologic point of view, Brudzeń Landscape Park and its buffer zone are characterised by a diversified relief and significant height differences as we visualised at the 3D-model (Fig.6). The highest is the northeast part of the Park, reaching 110 m a.s.l., and the lowest point is the Skrwa Prawa River outlet to the Vistula River at the height of 57 m a.s.l. (Fig.6).

So, we decided to choose the locations in the heights from 80-100 as the most suitable for the construction from the geologic-geomorphologic point of view.

Fig.8

Fig.9.

Criterion of soil conditions

Analysing the soil situation and distribution within the BLP we can distinguish that the soils within the BLP are poorly diversified comparing to the geological strata. We concluded that the

most suitable are *cambisols* and *podsol* soils as the most appropriate hydrogeological characteristics (Fig.8), and can be used for hotel construction and also because they have stable soils profile. In our location choice we avoid *half-bog* soils and *hydrogenic* soils that are characterised by the greatest ability to accumulate pollutions and whose formation is caused by the lowering of the groundwater table and may result in the interruption of peat-formation processes.

Criterion of vegetation conditions

Analysing the vegetation and ecological patterns in BLP we tried to avoid areas with forests and, of course, strictly reserved areas, riparian areas which are of high importance for the fluvial ecosystems. Also fresh forests are necessary to save from the anthropogenic intervention as well as forests mixed with coniferous forests as valuable for the environment, while meadows areas can be taken for the buildings construction. We also considered as unsuitable areas with vegetation communities of the specific forests which are characteristic and typical for the local environment (e.g. ash-alder forests, hombeam forest, oak forest, alder forest).

Analysing specific rare plants communities, we highlighted the areas of concentrated localization of such protected species as turk's cap lily, white water lily, yellow foxglove, dog lichen, ground pine, etc (12).

Criterion of ecological conditions

Looking at the Ecological structures map (Fig.10) we can see the zones with high importance of protection: the highest importance has areas of country-level ecological corridors as well as biocentres. Lesser yet also important zones are in *over-local* and *local corridors* (coloured in orange). By doing the overlay of the layer with our proposed hotel location and layer of ecological structures we avoided all these areas.

Criterion of hydrogeological conditions

We located our hotel in the distance of 30 m from the river bed, because the groundwater table inclines in the direction of the *Skrwa Prawa River* and the *Vistula River* valley. Therefore, the safest location will be in 30 meters at the least apart from both rivers.

Factor of human resources

Another important factor of our environmental assessment and evaluation was location of the planned hotel away from the existing areas of restoration protection zones, monumental buildings, cemeteries, parks and other valuable objects in cultural and historical point of view (Fig.11).

Criterion of spatial planning

Territories of both existing and proposed spatial planning have been analysed in careful way, because planned hotel construction must become a part of the existing purpose landscape within the park, including its anthropogenic and natural elements.

Therefore, we avoided all areas with buildings and services areas, tourism areas, individual recreational buildings, wastewaters treatment zones, etc (Fig.13)

The proposed locations of our hotel

- 1) This place is a good tourist location near the green area and in close proximity to the cities which will enable them all the advantages of the urban life, e.g. infrastructure, roads and transport systems, possibilities to visit cafes and restaurants, etc.
- 2)

II. GIS-Modelling

Future recommendations

For further studies within this topic the suggestion would be to include other factors for the evaluation criteria, because the increased amount of different various factors enable complex and thorough spatial analysis. For the GIS-part we would recommend to include satellite imagery for the additional raster processing which would enable to make more detailed analysis of the land cover classes within the area as well as to indicate vegetation patterns.

We also recommend for the further research additional consulting at the resource planning services and use additional materials concerning technical, hydrogeological and environmental conditions of the research area.

Discussions

Conclusions

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